

**POLITICS OF DEVELOPMENT IN KOKAN REGION
IN MAHARASHTRA**

Prof. Mahajan Viraj Dattatraya
Khare-Dhere –Bhosale College , Guhagar Dist- Ratnagiri

Introduction –

Since many years; the concept related with development is being studied from many dimensions. After the period of 1950, many eminent are taking preview of positivity created by social changes through many various developments, oriented programs. After 1990, India has accepted globalization, liberalization & policy of privatization. Through this, India market exposed to multinational companies & global capitalism. All fields like agriculture, finance, education, health, energy production, insurance & last but not least fishery experiences its effects. Cultural life & social principals can't remain unaffected from the influence of globalization. In short, effects of developmental policies leave an impression on various sectors. Especially in the Industrial field the effects are obvious a strong fillip for industrialization, & ensuing pollution in environment, displacement, rehabilitation struggle becomes regular routine. Through this, a developmental dilemma is being created.

Which concept of development has been intended by politicians, rulers & beurocracy implementing developmental plans, is mostly denied by the leaders & supporters of environmental movement. Because (it cause) through these developmental projects if the questions of various variety of species & displacement are arising then it can't be development. On the contrary, peoples are displacing & for that reason developmental projects shouldn't be implemented is defined by supporters of development. In short, what is to be achieved from development? These objects, view behind accepting these objects & life values entangled with each-other. Hence, state power is determining the developmental policies. On the governmental level the decision has been taken about which objects should be achieved? From where, the equipment may make available? & which programs should be implemented with great priority? Etc. People agree with government. In short, decision mechanism should be transparent is an ideal situation. The situation is different in reality. The question, are local people taken into confidence in developmental policy's implementation? Becomes noteworthy, In recent period, in this process many question arise like land acquisition, project planning, compensation, pollution, displacement & rehabilitation etc. Supporters & advocates have their own views (obvious). Through these clashes developmental politics takes shape.

Social Movement

The scope of social movement is quaintly speedy, complex & extensive. In the beginning of 20th century, social process, & changes, inspite of this as soon as realization of this process got acquired by scholars & observers, it came to light that movements are as old (ancient) as humans social life. Hence, scholars agree on the fact that social movements are regular & indivisible part of human life & (this social movements are) exceptional becomes as outdated opinion. In recent time, "Social movement" named study branch make new entry in various universities. It becomes very necessary to study the relation between social changes & their processes. In short the field of social movements pushes the boundaries to the possible extends. Not only scholars but also common man's daily life is mesmerized by the social movements. Because of the concepts of developmental projects / capitalized developments rehabilitation movements laid their foundation through the issues of common people's rehabilitation & land acquisition. Maximum movements result from the feeling of iniquity & being deceived by a state / political parties. Common man participates in the social movements through the feeling of finding out the solutions for their problems. He participates in the movements to voice out iniquity & to curb oppressive government.

While considering pervasive nature of social movements, to interpret it properly becomes impossible. Appearance & structure of social movements differ from region to region & so exact per part

can be arranged. In spite of this social movement's pervasion reaches to the extent of "United action done for the change transformation". In 20th century, social movements may be seen as "Social intervention of groups." But people's movements are not just social interventions but people's objectiveness, an intentional & discriminational action. Not only this but the object is to x- arrange the social structure. Social movement's importance has raised because positivity in views. Not only this but they get reputation also. In short, social movements are proving their objectives through the structural, developmental & sometimes through struggle some appearances. Through this efforts, different forms of movements has been created as constructive, rebellion, self-reliant, caring, political, without the sense of politics a common interest etc.

Environmental questions of India & social movements

The concept "Social movement" has been studied on different layers. Consequently, about their theorems similarity in opinion doesn't exist. Eminent have seen social movements as essential alternative to the way of representation / the prime political foundation. So the pervasiveness of social movements is somehow extentional, somehow informal than united political parties & special in attitude than common social streams. Desapotra, Diana & Dohetri have thrown the flood of light on the aspects of transitional side of social movements. GhanashyamShaha is looking at the social movements as an intentional united direction for the fulfillment of objectives. Some scholars think social movements as different / distinct from the political parties & liberal politics is a soul of social movements. In spite of this, questions in front of environmental movements related movements always remain the subject of discussion for -

It's not so that every environmental movement puts forth the thought of freedom from exploitation. According to Roots,"an environmental question is a social responsibility of the environmental movements. But while thinking about Indian environmental movements it's not enough to be socially responsible the most important is their action against state level structure & a thinkfull view." In short, Indian environmental movements are not just limited to the environmental / cleanness / nurtural but also fighting for the existence of local poor people.

To India environmental movements RamchandraGuha has given likeness an umbrella, In this local struggle, prominently for rights fought for self-existence, Chipko movements, campaign against silent valley dam of Kerala, Narmada's Bachaomovement etc. & all these movements are indicator of above aspect. After 1980, capital centered developmental policies cause strong fights against the biggest dams & projects of India. People builded the strong movements against many projects like Singrouli (U.P.), KoyalKaro, Suvernrekha (Zarkhand), Ukai, Mahi-kadana (Gujrat), Chilika (Orissa), Koyna (Maharashtra) etc. In all this matter, rehabilitation always remains an important issue. In short in India environmental movement the issues like rights of rehabilitants, distributive justice, rehabilitation, right to verify ,the claim of public interest being of project prove essential.

Politics of development in Maharashtra

In decade 1970's the environmental movements acquired a special recognition. Maharashtra was not exception to this serious questions related with established development got Voice but (how may be development?) established political parties & unions have similarity in opinion about development. Our political leaders dream to make India like New York, Bangkok, Hong Kong, California. On local level movements built up because of the movement's capital oriented developmental concept on expense of maximum exploitation of natural resources To the government by planning the huge dams. Couldn't solve the question of Koyana dam's rehabilitant became the reality. Koyana project's affected committee built up a social movement to sort out the questions like an environmental balance, destructive development, proper rehabilitation, etc. In the movement of dam affected, the contribution of Dr. Baba Adav&Dr. Bharat Patankar becomes noteworthy.

Many businessmen get attracted to Konkan because of its geographical situation. Thane & Raigad like district comes into light because of their juxtaposition to Mumbai Konkan becomes a golden land for chemical plants & power production plants because of many reasons like plenty water required for power plants, sea shower for disposal of polluted water, availability of sea ports for export – import of required raw material, transport facility for being connected with the rest of India by means of Konkan railway.

In Maharashtra, social movements built up because of power plants also. In 1990, the struggle against Enron became well known. In Enron Virodhi Kruti Sangharsh Samiti (Enron opposing action committee's) Right the issues an environmental balance, rehabilitation of affected, extended rate for power, sea-pollution & question of fishermen as well as the role of government in process of globalization- prove important. In 1992, starlight project had to move in Tamilnadu because of the oppose shown by local people of Ratnagiri. In recent year, the same issues came forth in case of social movement against "Jaitapur atomic energy plant" in Rajpur district of Konkan. The government wanted to oppress this movement by using its power. Instead of this in Konkan 14 energy plants are scheduled. Mahagencoscheduled coal energy plant becomes, controversial before land acquisition process intended to open in Dhopave, Guhagar. Local people are against it. The special thing to note down is the government has permitted to open 4 energy plants in the circumference of 40 km. Consequently people have grudge against government. In addition to this grudge, "Gail Company has started to lay down gas pipeline from Mumbai to Bangalore local people have a strong oppose to land acquisition on local level as well as dominance of company over local people. Local people have shown their oppose to Finolex & Jindal energy plants. But these two projects are taking effort for pushing themselves forth.

While discussing about Konkan, the government has permitted Dempo mining project in Kalane situated district Sindhudurg. In this project Local MLAS, ministers & political leaders lie their interest. Local people are struggling for last 5 years. But the government has given blind eye to this movement. Local people of village Velas situated in district Ratnagiri has started the same styled struggle against Ashapura mining company. In the legislative assembly of Maharashtra state government gives the orders against illegal excavation context. But in which way Goa is showing an open oppose to mining projects unitedly, Maharashtra lacks zeal. In this field in which way we can see the contribution of civil society conspicuously, in Maharashtra it is not happening. By doing the classical study civil society organization become successful in giving defeat to the lobby of mining companies.

In the decade of 80's a struggle prevailed in Konkan means fight against pollution. After the period of 1980, industries got expanded in Konkan. Industries got establishment through the medium of MIDC in Raigarh, Ratnagiri & minor margin in Sindhudurg. Majority of industries were chemical & because of this movements aroused about the pollution created by these industries. "Shramik Sahayog & Dabhol Char Gav Sangharsh Samiti" raised peoples movement against pollution created by MIDC Lote Parshuram nearby Chiplun. This pollution caused water-pollution. Local fishermen became jobless. Instead of this, main crops like mango & cashew nut got severely affected. Today also in this region HPCL project is being scheduled Government has started land acquisition. Kruti Samiti (Action committee) is formed as a prerequisite of social movement to show a strong oppose.

Raigad district is nearby Mumbai so the process of Industrialization starts earlier. Peasant's movements under the leadership of P.W.P.'s N.N. Patil became famous. Peasants of SEZ's announcement by the government in recent period Raigad district can be explained as a district affected by flood of SEZ in Maharashtra. In Raigad district 11 SEZ projects are intended. For that reason 50,000 Acre land acquisition will be done, the same land which is used by local people for the purpose of agriculture, salt (beds) pans, meadows for animals. SEZ project of Reliance Industry Ltd. Was intended to be being executed in 45 villages of three districts- Panvel, Pen & Uran. For that reason 14,000 hector lands had been acquired. To this project affected people of 45 villages showed oppose unitedly. Under the banner of civil society

organization project affected people opposed by forming committees like Mahamumbai SEZ against struggle committee, Action committee against globalization, Peasant workers party, National Alliance of people movement, 24 villages SEZ against struggle committee. LokShasanAndolan, KhetiBchaoSamiti etc. In 2006, Peasant Workers Party's leader MadanPatil showed his support to the movement. Consequently, P. L. Party gained victory in 2006's Z.P. election by winning 42 seats from 61. Further Z.P. sanctioned agreement against SEZ. By practicing means of rallies, discussions, Dharanas, picketing, Fasting, Mochas people showed their grudge to the government against SEZ project. Finally after the decision of Supreme Court, government had to scrap SEZ project. But still the government doesn't move back completely. Because the government plans land acquisition for small scale project. To this date also the government keeps buying the land through the medium of private brokers. Recently, newspapers publish the breaking news of 1875 hector land acquisition by Mahamumbai SEZ Company for the same purpose. Hence we can address this as a foundation for future people's movement.

Nine villages, Shahapur-Dherand village of district- Raigad including the struggle between the government versus peasant continues since two years. Land acquisition in this village will be done for electricity project. The required land would be being acquired from the local peasant so they show strong oppose to it. "Nine villages struggle committee" has built up a pervading social movement. In case of Balganga, Varsai dam project affected people; private developers have trodden all ethical laws by practicing oppression of local people. In this region dams will be constructed to satisfy raising quest for water of MMRDA. For second time, the villagers have to race the problem of migration.

After the period of 1990's, through the both aspects- support for developmental projects & oppose for the same- politics of development of Maharashtra began to shape up. Enron opposing movement & movements continue on the question of Jaitapur project are two fine examples of above mentioned. It's not necessary that the question what should be the concept of development? Should be discussed. The local groups in favor of project advocacy are related with the ruling parties. These groups forget advertantly to discussions should be started on the local levels first in the political conferences. While implementing particular projects in specific areas the related governing bodies like village administration, town administration & Z.P. members have been never taken in confidence. Considerably, project planning being charted in Mumbai / Delhi so local people do not included in it. Hence decision mechanism doesn't implemented in the democratic ways. As political power is decentralized in panchayat form relevantly it becomes necessary to decentralize decision mechanism. If it happens so then the oppose for such projects would be lesson. While implementing development projects to include local people in it becomes important. For implementing development projects systematically to consider issues of development oppose become pre-requisite. These projects are being opposed till today for the reasons like for local people are not taken into confidence by private / government sector, reasonable rate for land is not paid, beneficiary determined by rehabilitation act keep out of reach of the project affected, exploitation of arable land instead of arid's & an ignorance to the development of arid lands. Local people have been bluffed by showing a snare of job etc.

No one can deny development. But by taking into account the above issues, it becomes essential to think over policy leveled development for the government. The oppose for such developmental projects would be lesson by giving assurance of inclusion of local people in developmental projects & their proper rehabilitation. While thinking about Konkan in politics of development supporters & opponents have played a huge role. Because supporters claim about social-well-being caused by developmental projects but they are not taking a least mention also about verifying societal nature of social well fax of such developmental projects. Project opposing groups also take solace in the movements by not involving in such issues. Through that complexities the dilemmas about development get created. To break this

dilemmas a strong will-power is needed. This will-power has not been shown by both sides. So an entanglement of development process will keep continue.....

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